

A Review of Wi-Fi 6 : The Revolution of 6th Generation Wi-Fi Technology

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Abstract: *In the past few decades, there's been a massive increase in the number of Internet users, gadgets, and Internet connectivity-all around the world. These factors, combined with digital transformation in all industries worldwide and increasing utilization of bandwidth-demanding applications, have made significant contributions to the condition for the quicker and universal wireless network connection. To tackle these problems, the next-generation Wi-Fi needs to address the problem of low efficiency of the whole Wi-Fi network resulting from the access of more terminals. From 2014, the IEEE 802.11 working group started to address this challenge and anticipated to release 802.11ax also known as Wi-Fi 6 in 2019. Such a new standard is going to introduce technologies like uplink Multi-User MIMO (MU-MIMO), (OFDMA) Orthogonal frequency division multiple access, and higher-order coding 1024-QAM to resolve network capacity as well as transmission effectiveness problems in terms of spectrum resource use and multi-user access. One of the objectives of Wi-Fi 6 is to enhance the regular user throughput by at least four times as well as increasing the number of concurrent users by higher than three times within the dense-user environment in comparison with Wi-Fi 5. Wi-Fi 6 is the next-generation technology that is based on the IEEE 802.11ax standard. Such technology will allow the connectivity of next-generation Wi-Fi. Wi-Fi 6 will provide the coverage, capacity, and performance to efficiently meet the growing and changing use of Wi-Fi technology. Wi-Fi 6 is a brand-new jargon to readily understand Wi-Fi networking devices as well as its connectivity. This study will examine the various key characteristics and the new generational approach of Wi-Fi 6.*

Keywords: *Wi-Fi6, MU-MIMO, OFDMA, 802.11ax, IEEE, 1024-QAM, TargetWakeupTime(TWT).*

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I. INTRODUCTION

Each generation of Wi-Fi gives a chance to stop and take into account the transformational changes which will be influencing us in the coming years. These Days, Wi-Fi networks now are experiencing the bandwidth-demanding media content as well as multiple Wi-Fi gadgets for each user. The need for Wi-Fi access from the users has moved from a privilege to a necessity. Because of this, network efficiency has turned into a business-critical requirement. Both employees and consumers have arrived to expect a trusted Wi-Fi connection the lack of which can affect their decision to enter an establishment or to exit it. To attract and retain customers and employees, businesses need to provide dependable wireless and an incredible experience or run the risk of losing business. Moving ahead, networks will have to face a continuous dramatic rise in the number of devices, an increasing of the total worldwide IP traffic, as well as a wide variety of new technologies that will all heavily depend on Wi-Fi. Wireless technology is the backbone of life now at work, home, and on the move. Contained in nearly every smartphone, computer, as well as a tablet, Wireless functionality is a mandatory requirement for a growing range of equipment from televisions and household appliances to security systems as well as sensors. To adapt the increasing number of IoT devices, upgrades to the effectiveness of a Wi-Fi network as well as how it manages congestion and ever-growing capacity needs has become an important factor of success. Wi-Fi 6 promises to provide Better Throughput, lower latency, Higher Density, greater capacity, Enhanced coverage, Improved Determinism, Network slicing, Multi-Access Edge Computing, and improved security. With the anticipated increase in data needs that range from mission-critical to huge machine connectivity, deployment of Wi-Fi 6 has boosted expectations that this will open up new possibilities for manufacturing business models. Technological innovation has been driving numerous uses for Wi-Fi to market and facilitated developing opportunities for example in the virtual reality as well as high-definition telepresence. Prospects to link everybody and everything is rising. As with earlier generations, Wi-Fi 6 also known as 802.11ax will enhance high-density performance and deliver quicker throughput. Additionally, the new generation of Wi-Fi will enhance normal speed as well as concentration improvements with the new functionality designed specifically for the technology trends of the foreseeable future. Wi-Fi networks of the foreseeable future need to be quick and effective to adapt improved client density, high-level throughput requirements, as well as a wide range of

new applications. Wi-Fi 6 provides several new enhancements to make it the top-performing set of wireless protocols yet created. Wi-Fi 6 will not only improve the overall performance, although it is intended to perform effectively in real-world circumstances. New features like OFDMA, BSS color, TWT, uplink MU-MIMO, and latest modulation schemes all work together to enable the end-users to experience connectivity with no bottlenecks or a decrease in performance.

II. THE STANDARD BACKGROUNDS OF Wi-Fi TECHNOLOGY

The continuous innovation of Wi-Fi technology is primarily as well as particularly reflected in the transmission rate. With almost two decades' development, the transmission rate of Wi-Fi 6 is nearly Eight hundred and seventy-two times the first Wi-Fi 1 version.

When Wi-Fi 5 came out, an average US household had nearly 5 Wi-Fi devices with a growing tendency for 9 devices these days. Take Note that, the additional devices will be taking a toll on the network. Hence, the greater the devices demand Wi-Fi, the slower the network as a whole is going to be. For better bandwidth and improved performance, the latest technology is in immediate need.

III. FEATURES AND BENEFITS OF WIFI 6

Wi-Fi 6 is prepared to power completely new mobile experiences, providing faster speeds for immersive-experience applications along with more device and IoT capacity for high-density environments like shopping centers, stadiums, university lecture halls, and production facilities.

IV. TECHNOLOGICAL BENEFITS OF Wi-Fi 6

Wi-Fi 6 is bringing a substantial improvement via key enabling technologies such as MU-MIMO & OFDMA to accomplish faster and highly enhanced Wi-Fi performance. Wi-Fi 6 components support important technologies like TWT and 1024-QAM modulation to improve the data throughput, work at low-power consumption, and support up to 32 clients at the same time. Let us take a good look at some of the benefits of using Wi-Fi 6 technology.

TECHNOLOGICAL BENEFITS OF WiFi 6	
SIMULTANEOUS MULTI-USER TRANSMISSIONS	This is efficiently accomplished with MU-MIMO and OFDMA (two techniques that have been widely utilized in the cellular domain), by concentrating on the average throughput per station, rather than aggregate output. They are complimentary techniques in both directions (uplink and downlink) that efficiently serve diverse traffic types (e.g. text messages, video streaming, etc.) to multiple users concurrently. While MU-MIMO is useful when multiple users have full buffer traffic to send, OFDMA provides maximum benefit when multiple users have small amounts of data
INCREASED CAPACITY AND HIGHER DATA RATES	Through 1024QAM, Wi-Fi 6 can deliver a 25% increase in capacity over 256QAM, as in previous Wi-Fi generations, particularly at close distances.

TARGET WAKE TIME (TWT) IMPROVES POWER EFFICIENCY OF STATION	Target Wake Time (TWT), a feature in Wi-Fi 6 networks, lets routers schedule check-in times with devices. This enables the devices to plan communications with a router in advance, thus reducing the amount of time they need to keep their antennas powered on to transmit and search for signals. It improves the battery life of devices and routers for low-power Wi-Fi devices. The TWT mechanism was originally introduced in the IEEE 802.11ah amendment.
PERFORMANE IN HYPER -DENSE ENVIRONMENTS	Multiple Access Points deployed in dense device environments will be able to collectively deliver the desired QoS to clients with diverse usage profiles in Wi-Fi 6. It can dramatically increase the aggregate wireless network throughput to address high-density venues such as stadiums, auditoriums, retail chains, and malls, etc.
UPLINK RESOURCE SCHEDULING	This functionality is probably the most important innovation and challenging aspect of Wi-Fi 6 (802.11ax). With uplink resources scheduling, the AP deterministically allocates resources, coordinates and schedules the simultaneous transmission of multiple clients.
SPATIAL REUSE TECHNIQUE	Multiple APs operate on a shared channel by mitigating co-channel interference. This is made possible by a spatial reuse technique known as BSS Coloring, which enables devices in one BSS to ignore frames from other BSSs on the same channel, which are typically some distance away.
STRENGTHEN INDOOR AND OUTDOOR OPERATIONS	Wi-Fi 6 (802.11ax) includes mechanisms such as long OFDM symbols to optimize multi-path and supports robust outdoor deployments.

V. 6th GENERATION OF Wi-Fi SECURITY

Supplying data by using a wireless medium means that everyone is able to capture the signal. There can be no boundary, such as in the case of cable communication, that prevents inappropriate access. This means that we need to take additional security measures. This article will review the current Wi-Fi 6 security WPA3.

Wi-Fi Protected Access 3 (WPA3)

At the start of the year 2018, Wi-Fi Alliance declared that WPA3 is going to be introduced. The aim of WPA3 is to streamline security, enhance the cryptographic strength, and enable robust authentication. WPA3 is available in two variants WPA3-Personal and WPA3-Enterprise.

VI. Wi-Fi PROTECTED ACCESS 3 (WPA3)- PERSONAL

Wi-Fi PROTECTED ACCESS 3 (WPA3)-PERSONAL	
WPA3-Personal gives better protections to individual users by giving stronger password-based authentication, even if users choose passwords that fall short of usual complexity recommendations. This feature is enabled via Simultaneous Authentication of Equals (SAE), which replaces Pre-shared Key (PSK) in WPA2-Personal. This technology is resistant to offline dictionary attacks where an adversary attempts to determine a network password by attempting possible passwords without further network interaction.	
NATURAL PASSWORD SELECTION	Enables users to choose passwords which are easier to remember.
EASE OF USE	Delivers enhanced protections without any change in the way users connect to a network.
FORWARD CONFIDENTIALITY	Provides Protection For data traffic even if a password has been compromised after the data was transmitted.

Source: www.wi-fi.org

VII. Wi-Fi PROTECTED ACCESS 3 (WPA3)- ENTERPRISE

WPA3 is developed upon WPA2, but it provides several enhancements:

Wi-Fi PROTECTED ACCESS 3 (WPA3)-ENTERPRISE	
Governments, Enterprise, and Financial institutions have increased security with WPA3-Enterprise. WPA3-Enterprise builds upon WPA2 and ensures the consistent application of security protocols across the network. WPA3-Enterprise additionally offers an optional mode using 192-bit minimum-strength security protocols and cryptographic tools that will better protect sensitive data. The 192-bit security mode offered by WPA3-Enterprise ensures the right combination of cryptographic tools are used and sets a consistent baseline of security within a WPA3 network:	
AUTHENTICATED ENCRYPTION	256-bit Galois/Counter Mode Protocol (GCMP-256).
ROBUST MANAGEMENT FRAME PROTECTION	256-bit Broadcast/Multicast Integrity Protocol Galois Message Authentication Code (BIP-GMAC-256)
KEY DERIVATION AND CONFIRMATION	384-bit Hashed Message Authentication Mode (HMAC) with Secure Hash Algorithm (HMAC-SHA384)
KEY ESTABLISHMENT AND AUTHENTICATION	Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH) exchange and Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) using a 384-bit elliptic curve

Source: www.wi-fi.org

Although that's not everything that comes in this security update. Wi-Fi Alliance also declared Wi-Fi Enhanced Open which constitutes a response to a problem with open networks for example at airports, coffee shops, or shopping centers. Nowadays you can gain access to these networks without restrictions, frequently using some captive portal, although the traffic on the wireless connection has not been encrypted. Wi-Fi Enhanced Open shall provide unauthenticated data encryption based upon Opportunistic Wireless Encryption (OWE).

Synopsis of Wi-Fi Security: The most important conclusion from all earlier consideration is that WEP must always be prevented because many flaws were found. Devices that have old hardware must be updated to use WPA it uses a similar RC4 algorithm, although in a far safer way. It does not permit such frequent key collisions and introduces temporal keys. However, if a device offers hardware support for WPA2 it must be always used. It provides the best security in terms of message integrity as well as encryption. Wi-Fi 6 WPA3 will enhance all aspects of security significantly. Together, integrity and encryption are going to be at an even higher level, than we could presently accomplish with WPA2.

VIII. REASONS FOR UPGRADING TO Wi-Fi 6 FROM Wi-Fi 5

Earlier Wi-Fi standards, such as Wi-Fi 5, are equipped with two common issues: channel interference as well as wireless efficiency difficulties that are resolved by Wi-Fi 6. Numerous wireless client devices will attempt to connect at the same moment causing collisions. In areas that possess a high concentration of wireless access points, like hotels, trade shows, etc. Wi-Fi 6 can certainly play to their own strengths. Indeed, Wi-Fi 6 offers enhancements to capacity and effectiveness issues which enhance the overall functioning in the restricted frequency bandwidths. For companies, adopting the latest Wi-Fi 6 technology is an excellent choice for futureproofing. Wi-Fi 6 can be abundant in use cases. In most instances, Wi-Fi 6 may be a futureproof technology update from Wi-Fi 5 or a comprehensive wireless upgrade from an older legacy technology.

NORMAL USE CASES FOR Wi-Fi 6 IS ILLUSTRATED IN THIS CHART BELOW	
SECTORS	USE CASE
RETAIL	Since the technology advances with Point of Sales (POS) devices and the high bandwidth, the requirement might require an upgrade in wireless network infrastructure to meet the new demands. Wi-Fi 6 can help meet those growing demands.
PUBLIC-SECTOR	Since the public sector is becoming more technologically modernized, the need for high bandwidth, wireless capacity, and improved Wi-Fi efficiency is more of a requirement. An upgrade to Wi-Fi 6 would respond to the majority of the new technology advancements.
HEALTHCARE	Since the healthcare clinic and hospital steps towards more modernized technologies in x-ray, digital charting, and the virtual doctor visits all require a significant amount of bandwidth and wireless efficiency. An upgrade to the latest Wi-Fi 6 technology might help ease the high bandwidth demands and expected wireless efficiency.
MANUFACTURING	From AI assembly-line robots to autonomous delivery trucks, a majority or all of the new machinery or IoT will require high bandwidth and capacity. The upgrade to Wi-Fi 6 will meet new requirements and capacity.
FINANCIAL	Since financial companies are becoming more tuned in high bandwidth and zero delays streaming in order to comply with the daily stock market trader demands. The upgrade to Wi-Fi 6 can provide high bandwidth, better efficiency, and provide an increase in wireless capacity for the financial market.
HOSPITALITY	Due to the enormous demand in the technology and internet connectivity, an older version or legacy Wi-Fi systems incur slow bandwidth, a shortage of device connectivity, as well as a less secure internet connection. An upgrade to Wi-Fi 6 with hospitality will reply to the majority of the above concerns.
NON-PROFIT	The non-profit industries are becoming more and more technological. With the growth in digital signage, 4K streaming, and still managing voting booths may need a large requirement in bandwidth and wireless capacity. Upgrading to Wi-Fi 6 can comply with the new increase in requirements and future-proof wireless technology at the same moment.
LAW FIRMS	Since the industry has become more common in video conferencing, digital research, and cloud-based applications, law firms will require Wi-Fi to have faster bandwidths and better efficiency. Upgrade to the Wi-Fi 6 tests off the all-new prerequisite boxes added to futureproofs the Wi-Fi service within the coming years.
HOUSE OF WORSHIP	Houses of worship are becoming more and more reliant on getting great network connectivity, whether or not to help the worship team makes sure that everything runs smoothly or to enhance the congregation's experience. Above everything else, connectivity will need to be reliable, simple, affordable, and connect with every corner of the site. The newest in wireless technology satisfies all those needs.
EDUCATION	We are seeing a rise in video streaming, online classes, as well as other internet-based instruction. These need an enormous demand in bandwidth and capacity; that the older and legacy Wi-Fi technologies will not be able to always meet. Future-proofing the schools or institutions with Wi-Fi 6 will significantly increase the capability of being prepared for the soaring demand in bandwidth as well as a component of the digital revolution.

Source : www.netgear.com

IX. 6th GENERATION OF Wi-Fi WILL REDESIGN THE WORKING SPACE

Let us begin by taking a closer look at how the 6th generation of Wi-Fi redesigns the working space. Modern-day working spaces want to be able to create team-centric connections that will enable the team to share their knowledge and collaborate freely throughout the organization while at the same time keeping their part of the network private. Additionally, with more devices link the network including video conferencing systems, cameras, smart meeting rooms, and other IoT elements, we will require the capability to create scenario-driven services that correspond to the application needs. Security services might require low latency collaboration applications that might require high bandwidth, and smart asset tracking might require massive connectivity. You could imagine that with more than tens of millions of meetings happening per year all over the world, an enhanced digital office will be able to increase collaboration efficiency by 30% while at the same time improving user satisfaction.

Smart Meeting Room Management for effective operations and comfortable experience. With hundreds of meeting spaces and thousands of wireless HD screens, meeting room management can be a challenging task, utilizing Wi-Fi and Artificial Intelligence, we will be able to make the traditional meeting room smart by giving connectivity to wireless HD screens, wireless projectors, user laptops, and phones in addition to using room sensors for temperature and lighting. Additionally, we are able to provide smart signage outside the meeting-room doors that show real-time reservation and scheduling. We are also able to add smart whiteboards. Meeting room management enables the networking of key IT assets for preventative maintenance, online-resource management, and offers a connection between environmental systems and reservation systems for effective operations and a comfortable experience. If we look at the cubicle-based workplace, the 6th Generation of Wi-Fi offers a fully wireless environment for the internet and IP phones. The same network also integrates with other IoT systems, meaning technologies like ZigBee and Bluetooth are built in. This decreases deployment costs and enhances the overall time to market. Ultimately, in mobile office scenarios, employees are using a wide range of the device, and are continuously on the move, Seamless coverage, as well as roaming, becomes critical as a team member utilizes their phone for a video call, for instance, and then moves throughout the environment. The 6th Generation of Wi-Fi uses more intelligent methods to eliminate blind spots in corners and near windows to optimize the coverage for consistent service level experience.

X. 6th GENERATION OF Wi-Fi WILL REDESIGN THE PRODUCTION

Let us begin by taking a closer look at how the 6th generation of Wi-Fi redesigns the production. Industrial manufacturing is considered to be one of the earliest industries to adopt IT transformation and has a wide set of requirements. Beginning With VR- and AR-based planning, and design automated assembly as well as inspection, smart logistics plus pack planning, fleet management, robotics, and asset management. Each one of these will have its own requirements on bandwidth connection density, and latency. The 6th Generation of Wi-Fi will be able to enable 8K high-definition video. The high-definition video merged with Artificial Intelligence is currently being applied to recognize everything from passenger traffic patterns at airports to heat maps designed for the detection of forest fires. 8K HD video is used for surveillance in addition to inspection. The higher resolution makes it possible for more flexible camera placement as well as more accuracy in detection and identification. Unfortunately, high resolution comes at the expense in the form of bandwidth. Fortunately, the 6th Generation of Wi-Fi could easily support the ultra-high-bandwidth requirements of this new ultra-concept. In Smart Factories, the 6th Generation of Wi-Fi network is utilized for voice, data, and location, and it's critical for tracking part trays and ensuring the efficient operation of Automated Guided Vehicles. Raw material trays are tracked during the whole process while AGVs move the trays and avoid collisions. Power data information is also collected to optimize utilization which has resulted in significant energy savings while at the same time improving First Pass Yield and reducing the number of AGVs necessary.

In unmanned warehouses, the Automated Guided Vehicles communicates with each other through Wi-Fi 6 Network. By removing humans on the warehouse floor, it improves coordination, safety, and overall effectiveness of the warehouse operation while at the same time reducing costs. In such an environment, latency and packet loss could mean the difference between a highly successful warehouse operation and a complete business shutdown. By seamless coverage and latency as low as 10 ms, unmanned warehouses keep products flowing safely and efficiently.

XI. CONSTRUCTION SITES WILL BE TRANSFORMED BY THE 6th GENERATION OF Wi-Fi

To look at what it all means for the construction industry, we have to take a step backward and take a look at what smart technology can actually accomplish. The latest technology such as drones as well as wearable IoT sensors, at first sight, look out of place when talking about construction sites but as the industry

changes to meet the new requirements of the Twenty-first century it begins to become clearer what they have to offer. Construction sites are hazardous places, safety is vital however it is usually process-driven, technology can aid in this crucial area.

The following are several ways in which construction sites may be able to take advantage of up and coming technology in order to make construction sites to a more secure place to work. The usage of drones meant for streaming high-quality video from the top of the site can be viewed remotely through experts to minimize risk when designing for critical procedures. Vehicles fitted with network-connected reversing cameras can be linked to AI systems as well as network-connected vehicles to only allow a vehicle to shift backward whether it is safe to achieve this. IoT devices that can be worn showing workers critical signs like heart rate might be monitored in real-time to guarantee the workers at high altitudes or in hazardous areas are functioning within secure physiological limits. Position tracking of workers by way of triangulation of Wi-Fi signals can guarantee the safety and implement security, tracked through wireless devices back to cloud solutions that could alert the appropriate teams if the procedures and standards are broken. These are just a few instances within the safety features of the modern construction site, and they depend on fast, secure, stable wireless networks. Tomorrow's construction sites are going to be safer, more effective, and much more automated although that can occur only with fast, safe, and reliable networks in place, and currently, Wi-Fi 6 provides just that.

XII. Wi-Fi 6: EMPOWERING A MOBILE WORKFORCE

The initial type of prospective differentiation really taps into a trend concurrently surrounding industry at present. Mobile, isolated, and flexible working has proved to be a natural result of the growth of IoT and BYOD, although companies particularly SMEs have frequently had to continue into these areas with extreme caution thus far. It is safe to say that by Wi-Fi 6, performance in congested or fragmented areas will cease to be a concern. Not just that, but the entire period accessible to employees looking to go away from their desks as well as to go mobile shall also be improved along with the promise of extended battery life in accordance with the watch of Wi-Fi 6. Basically, speed enables mobilization a concept should not be overlooked when so much job desirability is connected to the employee flexibility at the moment. This will not only be expanding the office landscape but making a company more attractive to potential recruits through the process.

XIII. Wi-Fi 6: PROVIDING BENEFITS TO THE SUPPLY CHAIN

Enhanced speed, effectiveness, and efficiency throughout internal systems are also going to be extremely attractive to business associates and fellow partners along the supply chain. The scope of deployment is significantly improved by enhanced network speeds, producing an equally remarkable range of opportunities to subscribers, as well as business associates. Tapping in a new Wi-Fi experience is going to bring both sets of relationships what they are looking for above everything else during normal business transactions unparalleled efficiency, quality, and safety along with reduced risk.

XIV. Wi-Fi 6: BENEFITS TO THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

The automotive market might turn out to be as near as there exists to a wholly innovative segment for Wi-Fi 6. The Automotive sector, moreover, has now been in revolutionary mode as it is preparing to present the first vehicles equipped with integrated 5th Generation (5G) cellular in 2022. The Automotive industry is hard at work on new uses for 5G integration for vehicle communication. Take self-driving cars, for instance, communication between vehicles will be vital for avoiding accidents as well as for speeding halt and go traffic. Similarly, vehicle-to-infrastructure will be able to help reduce energy-wasting waits and enhance the traffic flow at stoplights. Enhanced cellular connection to the internet is providing rise to two in-vehicle Wi-Fi access points, each one with vastly different purposes one for within the cabin, mainly for streaming entertainment as well as internet connection and secondly for diagnostics, through the air improvements as well as other telematics applications. In-vehicle entertainment is a developing fragment that will get an enormous lift from Wi-Fi 6 and 5G, since the mix will give ongoing responsiveness needed to A/V streaming, inside the vehicle. And afterward, on the telematics front, automobile sellers are energetic about the standpoint for interfacing wirelessly to vehicles on-board demonstrative devices while they pull right to the service area. This was not viable before Wi-Fi 6, because of the sheer amount of on-board diagnostic data in conjunction with the absence of a high-capacity, low-latency network in order to capture it quickly enough. In only the moment when the vehicle pulls into the service area, representatives will now be able to approach with a complete list of issues together with a repair estimate. Which will cut waiting periods and enhance the capacity of the service department a win-win situation for clients and the dealers.

XV. THE ADVANTAGES OF Wi-Fi 6 IN HEALTHCARE

Wi-Fi 6 refers to use instances the place there are a number of gadgets in a single space. Hospitals are the best occasion of congested, high traffic, consistently altering environments that will gain from Wi-Fi 6.

Wireless is large in hospitals furnished with the many advantages that it offers. Devices are connected and communicating for precise patient records as well as real-time data analysis. Nurses will be able to monitor several patients remotely from a single main station, obtaining alerts and observing data captured every second about their health. Doctors will be able to make informed choices with precise and up-to-date information about patients, which leads to better patient outcomes. Patients will be able to feel secure, in the knowledge that they will forever receive the proper dosage of the correct medication. Though, with an increasing number of Wi-Fi devices comes plenty of noise. Hospitals remain dynamic buildings with many Wi-Fi devices per person, unpredictability with individuals and devices continually on the move, as well as the noise from the other technologies. Wi-Fi 6 concentrates on the entire surroundings and bettering the standard hospital wi-fi experience for each and every Wi-Fi device. All such wireless gadgets imply that everybody is fighting for the resources and it changes dynamically. Therefore, Wi-Fi 6 creates network effectiveness by applying the features and advantages discussed above. Though device throughput might not be especially faster, everything is simply more organized and effective. Wi-Fi 6 removes the contention that makes everything operate better, and everybody has a superior wireless experience. For instance, wireless-enabled medical devices such as infusion pumps may be able to take advantage of scheduling-based resource distribution. Together with other devices as well as WAPs, the infusion pump may be able to negotiate and specify a particular time to send data, decreasing contention as well as the overlap between users. Through OFDMA, up to 30 other devices may share a channel with the infusion pump, instead of taking turns. As a consequence, the infusion pump will be able to see reduced power consumption from substantially improved sleep time and might even drop fewer packets. Wi-Fi 6 allowed infusion pumps, as well as different Wi-Fi medical devices, will perform better, stay linked better, will be extra relied on for a usual better experience.

XVI. TYPES OF COMPANIES THAT WOULD BENEFIT FROM DEPLOYING Wi-Fi 6

Companies presently running Wi-Fi 4 (802.11n) and below: The Study has estimated that up to 49 percent of all companies continue to run Wi-Fi 4 somewhere within the organization. The technology is nearly a decade old and may cause significant problems with application performance and reliability. Such customers must skip Wi-Fi 5 (802.11ac) and then deploy Wi-Fi 6. Implementing Wi-Fi 5 will probably cause the need to perform an additional upgrade within the next two to three years, if Wi-Fi 6 is installed it can be left in place for at least five years.

Pioneering businesses that are early adopters of new technology: Many companies try to stay ahead of the curve with regard to technology. Wi-Fi 6 will be able to provide the best experience for their clients as well as internal employees, the technology must be the highest consideration for these kinds of businesses. These businesses are frequently found in highly competitive industries, for example in luxury retail and entertainment facilities, as well as poorly performing wireless, can rapidly drive their customers to a different brand.

Companies that utilize high-bandwidth as well as immersive applications: Many companies have integrated high-bandwidth applications in their business processes. Instances of this are Virtual Reality (VR) as a customer service or collaboration tool, as well as HD video in enterprise workspaces and conference rooms. The increasing bandwidth of Wi-Fi 6 will guarantee improved user experience.

Businesses that are constructing high-density wireless networks: This encompasses public spaces, stadiums, universities, and theaters. These kinds of businesses are frequently trying to catch usage data about their audience; therefore, they need individuals to sign in to the Wi-Fi. With earlier versions of Wi-Fi, the wireless network gets saturated quickly, which causes individuals to switch to LTE. Use cases such as this have been extremely difficult to implement with earlier versions, although it's possible with Wi-Fi 6.

XVII. REVIEW OF Wi-Fi 6 DEVICE MARKET

Increasing Number of Consumer Electronics Devices (CED): Wi-Fi 6 devices market is expected to grow because of the substantial increase in the use of CED like laptops, tablets, and smartphone devices. Additionally, an increasing number of connected devices will require greater concurrent device capacity. Wi-Fi 6 gadgets or 802.11ax standards are anticipated to influence the latest Wi-Fi technologies or specifications and push the Wi-Fi 6 devices market soon.

XVIII. ENVIRONMENTAL CIRCUMSTANCES AND SECURITY THREAT CHALLENGES TO CONTROL MARKET GROWTH

Wi-Fi 6 devices are increasingly becoming improved with advances in technology. Though, the usage of high radio frequency ranges is influencing user health and harming the environment. Such factors are expected to hamper the Wi-Fi 6 device's market growth. Furthermore, increasing cybersecurity violations via wireless device networks are going to impede the growth of the Wi-Fi 6 devices market.

XIX. CONCLUSION:

This research paper presents an assessment of the 6th generation of Wi-Fi technology. Wi-Fi 6 will allow consumers to easily comprehend and to experience high-performance Wi-Fi technology. More importantly, Wi-Fi 6 brings network effectivity up to a stage that will enable modern new applications in nearly every segment. Few of these applications are already evident. However, many will not occur for several years, as long as there is a critical mass of Wi-Fi 6 connections. Now, it must be apparent that Wi-Fi 6 is going to deliver with it on the spot advantages in network speed, capacity, and responsiveness to the large market benefits that will enhance as time goes on as more Wi-Fi 6 capable devices which will be able to get the most of the technologies' several abilities replace systems that have early-generation connectivity. Every technology and business monitors are showing that Wi-Fi 6 has the ability to transform production and, over time, will enhance productivity. Whilst Wi-Fi 6 has the ability to bring numerous solutions. The latest upgradation and the comparison to current wi-fi technology. 1024-QAM, OFDMA, and enhanced MAC features of wi-fi 6 are going to bring improved performance experience for wireless users. Wi-Fi 6 is going to additionally bring even greater capabilities to provide support for smart homes, IoT, and the environment with large-scale implementations. In summary, providing fast and reliable wireless coverage in high-density implementation circumstances with the older Wi-Fi 5 (802.11ac) WAPs is becoming increasingly difficult as streaming 4K video, as well as other forms of immersive content, is becoming the standard. This is exactly why the 6th Generation of Wi-Fi (802.11ax) standard provides up to a four-times capacity rise over its Wi-Fi 5 (802.11ac) precursor. Through Wi-Fi 6 (802.11ax), multiple WAPs positioned in complex device environments will be able to collectively deliver necessary QoS to more customers together with more varied usage profiles. In our view, Wi-Fi 6 (802.11ax) is currently playing a significant role in assisting wireless to develop into a collision-free, deterministic Wi-Fi technology that dramatically increases cumulative network throughput to tackle the problem of high-density places and beyond.

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